

The Strategic Management of Mosque-Based Education

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ABSTRACT: As in the early days of Islam, mosques are not only places of worship but also places of empowerment and Islamic education for Muslims. As an Islamic educational institution, fostering personality attitudes, and the center of civilization for the people, mosques should be managed with modern, professional and accountable organizational management, following the management stages, in order to facilitate the service function for mosque congregations. Among these stages is to develop a good plan, which contains the formulation of actions to achieve the results according to the goals set, namely a decision on what to do in the future. This study uses a descriptive method with the aim of describing various phenomena that exist in the research location. The data collection techniques are through observation, interviews and documentation studies. The results showed that the planning of strategic management for mosque-based education used several strategies to develop, prosper the mosque, with the formulation starting with the development of the vision and mission, identifying various opportunities and threats as well as strengths and weaknesses faced by the *al-Mukarromah* mosque, determining the good goals for the mosque in short-term, medium-term and long-term goals, and determine alternative strategies and specific strategies to achieve.

KEYWORDS: Education, Management, Mosque, Strategic

INTRODUCTION

The mosque as an educational center has existed since the early days of Islam, namely the time of the Prophet Muhammad. Because the mosque which was founded by the Prophet Muhammad (Peace Be Upon Him) not only functions as a place of worship, but also functions as a means of fostering faith, fostering community, strengthening *ukhuwah Islamiyah*, struggle and means of *tarbiyah* (education). Prophet Muhammad built the first mosque in Medina with the aim of enlightening the people and introducing the divine message, the mosque was also used to carry out socio-religious activities in an effort to develop Islamic society (Yani, 2012).

At present, mosques are still able to carry out their roles and functions, as happened in the past. The existence of a mosque is very potential, especially in empowering Muslims. The slogan "back to the mosque" became the initial inspiration for the emergence of the spirit of restoring the glory of Islam from the mosque. This shows the importance of a mosque-based education process, a gentle education process, not violence. Therefore, it is necessary to have a better mosque management process, namely a good and modern mosque management strategy.

Mosque administrators (*takmir*) must be able to adapt to changing times. The management of the mosque in conventional and traditional ways will only make it very difficult for the mosque to develop, instead of getting more advanced, but getting further and further behind. The mosque will continue to be in a stagnant position, which will eventually be abandoned by the congregation. Mosques must progress and develop dynamically following the rhythm of the times. Mosques should not be left without efforts to improve and improve their management. Therefore, innovation is needed, continuous improvement, so that the management of the mosque is in line with the times, so that it is not abandoned by the congregation.

As an educational institution, fostering personality attitudes, and the center of civilization for the people, the mosque should have a strong allure to its congregation (*ummah*), including children who will become the successors of the congregation. This allure becomes a kind of "*ammunition*" that is powerful for increasing its role and function. Therefore, mosque management is needed to be oriented towards modern, professional and accountable organizational management. In this way, the management of the mosque is packaged in such a way, by following the stages of management, in order to facilitate the service function for the congregation of the mosque (Rifa'i & Fakhuraji, 2005).

Therefore, in the management of modern mosques, strategic management is needed, which is an art and science of formulating, implementing, and evaluating strategic decisions between functions that enable an organization to achieve its goals in

the future (Wahyudi, 1996). According to Nawawi (2003) strategic management is a process or series of decision-making activities that are fundamental and comprehensive, accompanied by the determination of how to implement it, which is made by top management, and implemented by all levels within an organization, to achieve its goals.

Although strategic management initially grew and developed among business, industry and the military. However, in subsequent developments, strategic management is also needed in various businesses and activities, including educational organizations and also in managing mosques. In the modern world, where the development of various disciplines and technology is highly rapid, there is not a single organization that does not use management. The management of mosques today, which is marked by the era of globalization, must face various challenges and very complex problems. This situation encourages mosque managers to prepare good and quality management, which is called strategic management. So that the goals in the mosque organization can be easily achieved effectively and efficiently.

In its implementation, the strategic management of mosque-based education should not be separated from the guidance of the *Qur'an* and *Sunnah*, not apart from the values contained in the *Qur'an* and *Sunnah*, in accordance with what was done by the Prophet Muhammad, at the time early Islam. The management of the mosque is carried out professionally and leads to a modern management system, so that it can anticipate the ever-changing developments in the life of an advanced and quality society. Therefore, good mosque management is needed (professional and modern based on the values contained in the *Qur'an* and *Sunnah*). The better the educational program managed by the mosque, ideally it will produce good output. If the mosque does not implement the principles of strategic management in its management, then the mosque can be abandoned by the congregation, especially the children (as the next generation)---because the mosque is less creative, innovative and responsive in meeting the needs of children, as the next generation of a prosperous mosque as *syi'ar* or greatness of Islam.

Good management is determined by good planning as well. Planning is a very important factor in modern management systems; it becomes a determinant and gives direction to the goals to be achieved. Planning greatly affects the success or failure of a management activity. Planning is the whole process of thinking and determining carefully about the things that will be done in the future in order to achieve the goals that have been set (Syamsudin, 2017).

Regarding the strategic management of mosque-based education, planning also occupies a strategic position in the overall strategic management process of mosque-based education. Planning provides clarity of direction and flow of the strategic education management process, so that with the existence of management planning (institutions) education can be more effective and efficient. Because the purpose of planning management is that all organizational activities are always focused on the goals and objectives that have been set.

In a management system, planning becomes important due to several factors. *First*, with planning, a direction of activity will grow. There will be guidelines for implementing activities aimed at achieving goals. *Second*, with planning, it is possible to make a forecast or foresight in taking a better step during the implementation period. *Third*, planning provides an opportunity to choose various alternatives on the best way of implementation. *Fourth*, with planning, it is possible to prepare a priority scale. And *Fifth*, with planning there will be a standard for conducting supervision or work evaluation.

THEORETICAL STUDIES

Prajudi Atmusudirjo in Syaifudin (2009) states that planning is the calculation and determination of something that will be carried out in achieving certain goals by a person or group. Tjokroamidjojo said that planning is a process of systematically preparing activities that will be carried out to achieve certain goals. Meanwhile, M. Fakry defines planning as the process of making various decisions that will be carried out in the future to achieve predetermined goals. Planning can also be interpreted as a process of making a series of policies to control the future as determined.

Based on some of the opinions above, it can be concluded that planning contains the formulation of actions to achieve the results according to the goals and objectives set. Planning is a decision on what to do in the future. Planning must be dynamic, continuous, flexible as an important thing in every effort to achieve a predetermined goal.

Educational planning as stated by Coombs is a rational application of a systematic analysis of the educational development process with the aim of making education more effective and efficient and in accordance with the needs and objectives of students and society. Beeby C.E. in Asnawir (2005:15), educational planning is the application of forecasts in determining policies, priorities, economics and politics, the potential of the system to develop, the interests of the state and community services that are

included in the system.

Furthermore, as stated by Banghart and Trull, there are several stages that should be passed in planning preparation. *First*, need assessment, which means conducting a study of various needs or estimates needed in the management process. At this stage the study must be carried out carefully and precisely, because it will provide input on program achievements. *Second*, the formulation of goals and objectives, which means the formulation of planning goals and objectives to be achieved. At this stage the formulation of objectives must be based on the vision, mission and the results of an initial study of various needs or an assessment of the required services. *Third*, policy and priority setting, which means the stage of designing the formulation of policy priorities to be implemented in the service. At this stage it is explained into a clear basic service strategy, in order to facilitate the achievement of goals.

Fourth, program and project formulation, is the formulation of programs and projects for the implementation of educational planning operational activities. *Fifth*, feasibility testing, is a feasibility test phase regarding various resources, both internal and external resources, human resources and material resources. If the plan is prepared based on the available resources carefully and accurately, it will produce a good level of plan feasibility. *Sixth*, plan implementation, is the stage of implementing the plan to realize the goals that have been set. One indicator of the success of this stage is largely determined by the quality of human resources in an organization, the pattern of cooperation as a reliable team work, supervision and control of activities during the process of implementing or implementing service programs. *Seventh*, the evaluation and revision stage for future plans, is an activity to evaluate the success rate of program implementation or educational planning, as feedback, then revision of the program for the next better service plan is carried out.

Furthermore, in preparing the plan, the following conditions must be considered: the planning must be based on clear objectives that are simple, realistic and practical in detail and contain all descriptions and classifications of activities and series of actions, so that they are easy to guide and carry out, have flexibility so that they are easily adapted to needs. as well as the conditions and situations that are carried out so that there is no duplication in implementation (Tilaar, 1998). The management process must run in accordance with planning, organizing, implementing and controlling. A management will function well if the target object is clear and its implementation is in accordance with what was planned (Surya, 2011).

Strategic planning is a leadership instrument and a process that will determine what the organization wants in the future and how it will achieve it; a process that defines goals. Even strategic planning is a process in making strategic decisions to formulate and implement strategic decisions and allocate resources to support work units and levels within the organization (Ramli, 2014). Furthermore, Taylor mentions that strategic planning is seen as a method for managing unavoidable change so that it can also be referred to as a method for dealing with environmental complexities which are often closely related to organizational interests. However, strategic planning is also a method to take the complexity of the internal environment caused by the various needs of each work unit in the organization.

Strategic planning in a more implementable understanding, as stated by Stainer is a logical framework that determines where you will be, where you will go, and how you will get there. It is also a process that directs leaders in developing a vision to describe the desired future. Planning changes the way management thinks about, allocates and reallocates resources, while program implementation takes place. In other words, planning deals with the future impact of decisions made now or also known as the future of current decisions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative approach and descriptive method, which is a research method aimed at describing or describing existing phenomena. (Sukmadinata, 2005). With this method, the researcher aims to make a systematic, actual and accurate description of the facts, characteristics and relationships between the phenomena being investigated (Nazier, 1998). Descriptive research is used in this study, for several reasons. *First*, the description or depiction of what is is a natural thing and in accordance with the reality of life, humans live as they are. *Second*, descriptive research has a clearer and more detailed meaning than the situation as it is. *Third*, in descriptive research, researchers do not manipulate or treat certain activities, circumstances, events, aspects, or components, but run as they are (Sukmadinata, 2005).

The data collection techniques in this study were using observation, interviews and documentation studies. Observation technique is a technique of collecting data by making direct observations of existing phenomena; in this case the researcher goes

directly to the research location (Ali, 1983). The interview technique is carried out by conducting a dialogue between the two parties, between the researcher and the informant who has been previously determined. The documentation technique used in the research is to study documents related to the research theme contained in the research location, in this case the *al-Mukarromah* Mosque, North Cikarang, Bekasi Regency.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Profile of *al-Mukarromah* Mosque

The *al-Mukarromah* Mosque was originally a mosque with a classic building that stands firmly in Cikarang, Bekasi Regency, precisely in the village of Karang Indah, North Cikarang District, which was established in 1986. Now the mosque that stands majestically is located on Jalan R.E. Martadinata Number 45, Cikarang Village, Cikarang District City, was once a small prayer room. The existence of the *al-Mukarromah* mosque is very beneficial for all circles of society, considering the very strategic location of the *al-Mukarromah* Mosque, which is next to the Cikarang Market, which is surrounded by immigrants from various parts of the region. This mosque was established in a location very close to shopping and commercial centers and Cikarang is a residential center for employees who work in the largest industrial area in Southeast Asia, with the aim that even though they are busy making a living working in industrial areas, they do not forget to worship Allah almighty. The position of the mosque which is on the side of the main road makes the *al-Mukarromah* Mosque a mosque that is very well known by the congregation from various corners as a means of worship and transit when people are traveling.

The shape of the design of the *al-Mukarromah* Mosque is a combination of local and Middle Eastern designs, this can be seen from the shape of the pyramid roof which is a characteristic of local Indonesian buildings, while the ornaments that adorn the profile and design of the mosque are very artistically detailed. The dome is a characteristic of the Middle East with a modern dressing. The appearance of the mosque which is very wide and extends to the side indicates that many worshipers use the *al-Mukarromah* mosque as a means of worship, both on weekdays, Friday worship, as well as on Islamic religious holidays, such as Eid al-Fitr and Eid al- Adha. This mosque is equipped with 2 front and side plazas that can accommodate worshipers if the mosque is full.

Al-Mukarromah Mosque sets the vision and mission, namely, “*Making the mosque as a center for worship, education and empowerment of Muslims, so that a prosperous mosque can be realized, based on faith and piety to Allah almighty*” Its missions are (1) to make the mosque a place to worship Allah almighty, and to become a cultural center for Muslims, (2) to make the mosque a welfare development and empowerment of the people through charity, infaq and alms activities, and (3) to make a mosque as a place of Islamic education for children, youth and adults through the *Al-Qur'an* Education Centre, and religious training”.

As a mosque located in an urban location, *al-Mukarromah* Mosque is equipped with various adequate facilities, including: (1) a place for prayer that is different from mosques in general, where the prayer places for men and women are only separated by a hijab. *Al-Mukarromah* mosque where male and female worshipers pray in separate buildings that are comfortable for each other, (2) adequate, very representative, and separate ablution places for men and women, and accommodate a lot of water, so that they do not feel lacking when many worshipers perform worship and ablution at the *al-Mukarromah* mosque. The place for ablution is well designed, so that the pilgrims feel comfortable performing ablution, (3) Automated Teller Machines (ATM) rice which are designed to serve users to issue a certain amount of rice. ATM measuring 60 cm x 60 cm x 160 cm, in the form of a small box or cupboard, with a capacity of about a quarter of a ton of rice, which users are not as complicated as ATM in general, which are used at ATM in banks, (4) adequate parking spaces in the courtyard of the mosque which was built using a fairly wide block, equipped with guards who regulate and guard the vehicles parked in the courtyard of the mosque, (5) *Al-Qur'an* Education Centre (TPA/TPQ). The education of the congregation is carried out in addition to the *Majlis Ta'lim* also carries out children's education programs with the TPA / TPQ education system, with the aim of providing education and teaching reading the Qur'an to students from an early age, as well as providing an understanding of the basics of Islam.

Strategic Planning

The management planning of the *al-Mukarromah* Mosque, Cikarang North, Bekasi Regency, uses several strategies to develop, prosper and advance the mosque. To be successful in the implementation, a good strategy is needed. Strategy will determine the success of implementing the development of the *Al-Mukarromah* Mosque in achieving its goals.

In management theory, planning, organizing, implementing and supervising are the four management functions needed in order to achieve the objectives of implementing the *al-Mukarromah* mosque development strategy. With these four management functions, it will facilitate the implementation of work programs smoothly in accordance with the vision, mission, and goals that have been set.

Planning is an activity that is preceded by making plans to achieve predetermined goals. This is in line with what the *al-Mukarromah* mosque has implemented, especially in implementing the visitor service strategy (congregational worship). In making an activity, of course, the first thing to do is develop a plan or strategy. To develop the management of the *al-Mukarromah* mosque, the point is, by serving mosque visitors (congregations), starting from the service of entering the mosque they are informed about what things must be done when they want to enter the mosque such as placing sandals/shoes, taking ablution water, and places of prayer, as well as other activities.

The provision of a library is part of the services of the *al-Mukarromah* mosque. The library provides various kinds of books for visitors to the mosque (congregation) to read. Provision of guides, if visitors want to know more about the *al-Mukarromah* mosque, in addition, a garden is also provided to relax with independent photo spots for visitors if they want to capture their moments.

Al-Mukarromah Mosque in addition to being a place of worship is also a place of education and guidance for the people. In its management run a modern management system. The planning of various activities carried out by the *Al-Mukarromah* mosque is prepared at the beginning of each year. The financial plan is compiled in the form of a Mosque Revenue and Expenditure Budget Plan (RAPBM) which is prepared by involving all stakeholders in the mosque environment.

Al-Mukarromah Mosque also always makes the mosque's annual plan (RTM) which is prepared by involving all stakeholders, both the core management of Mosque Prosperity Board (DKM), local government elements, and also involving the Mosque Youth Association (IRMA). Annual planning is as an important part of the modern management process in order to create an atmosphere and climate for professional mosque management.

Formulation of Strategic Management of Mosque-Based Education

The formulation of the strategic management development of mosque-based education is carried out by developing a vision and mission, identifying various opportunities and threats as well as strengths and weaknesses faced by the *al-Mukarromah* mosque, determining short-term, medium-term and long-term goals, and determining alternative strategies and specific strategies to achieve.

1. Development of vision and mission

The vision of the *al-Mukarromah* mosque is "To make the mosque a center of engagement and education and empowerment of Muslims, so that a prosperous mosque can be realized based on the values of faith and piety" Its missions are (1) to make the mosque a place to worship Allah, and to become a cultural center for Muslims, (2) to make the mosque a welfare development and empowerment of the people through charity, infaq and alms-giving activities, and (3) to make a mosque as a place of Islamic education for children, youth and adults through the al-Qur'an Education Centre, and religious training."

Based on the vision and mission above, in order to manage the mosque in a good direction, the main thing is to develop the mosque's vision and mission. According to the chairman of mosque prosperity board or knows as *DKM* of the *al-Mukarromah* mosque, "The development of the Vision and Mission is the focus of the implementation of the management of the *al-Mukarromah* mosque. This is done in addition to carrying out the process of coaching the congregation but also trying to educate students towards a better direction from year to year". The same thing was conveyed by several administrators of the *al-Mukarromah* mosque, the formulation of strategic management of mosque-based education in developing children's personalities in the indicators of developing vision and mission. "Development of Vision and Mission is a mandatory activity because it is in accordance with our goals in developing students' personalities".

Based on the explanation above, it can be seen that related to the development of the vision and mission, it can be concluded that the vision is a comprehensive statement about everything that is expected by an organization in the future and is made as a guide or direction for the long-term goals of the organization, while the mission describes the will of the organization. A good vision and mission statement presents the organization's uniqueness, reasons for existence, and encourages various stakeholders to move towards a common goal.

2. Identifying opportunities and threats external to the organization

The next step in forming a strategic management development formulation for mosque-based education is to analyze various opportunities and threats that come from external organizations, in this case the *DKM* of the *al-Mukarromah* mosque. Based on the results of interviews with indicators identifying opportunities and external threats of the organization with the chairman of the *DKM* of *al-Mukarromah* mosque, that the identification we did was to observe the behavior of students who differed in habits between at home and at school, many reports from parents that after attending school in children's mosques become passionate about learning and memorizing, so that the teachers take advantage of that opportunity to include assignments and memorization." Thus, identification of strengths and weaknesses is formed, evaluating capacity or ability to respond to issues, problems, and opportunities.

3. Determining internal strengths and weaknesses

The next step is to determine the internal strengths and weaknesses of the organization. Based on the results of interviews with indicators determining internal strengths and weaknesses with the chairman of mosque prosperity board or knows as *DKM* the *al-Mukarromah* mosque, that "Our school has strengths and attractions for new students to enter mosque education because the costs are quite affordable with the quality of religious education is quite good. Our weakness is the limited number of teachers, it is very difficult to get competent teachers. This is according to several administrators of the *al-Mukarromah* mosque because the costs are affordable so that all people can enter. And it becomes another strength that the educational institutions in the *al-Mukarromah* mosque are very strategically located and in the historic mosque environment.

Based on some of the explanations above, it can be concluded that related to the strategic management formulation of mosque-based education in developing children's personality, indicators determine internal strengths and weaknesses, both strengths and weaknesses are aspects that focus on internal aspects of the organization. Strength is a capability possessed by an organization that is relatively better. Meanwhile, weaknesses are organizational limitations in terms of resources, skills, and abilities, which are obstacles to organizational growth.

4. Creating long-term goals

Based on the results of interviews with indicators of creating long-term goals in the formulation of the problem formulation of strategic management of mosque-based education in developing children's personalities, the head of mosque prosperity board or knows as *DKM* of said that the long-term goal was to plan to build schools with higher levels because efforts to build students' personalities were not interrupted due to continuing in public school. Mosque-based religious education institutions are very urgent in fostering the personality of students, especially those in the mosque environment. Therefore, the long-term goal is to produce students with Islamic personalities, namely to form students' characters with Islamic personalities to prepare for socializing with the wider community.

Based on the explanation, it can be concluded that the goals themselves are divided into two, namely long-term goals and short-term goals. Long-term goals are reflected in the form of the organization's vision, which has a period of ten to twenty years into the future, while short-term goals, also known as destination statements, are derivatives of the mosque's vision, in the form of goals to be achieved in a shorter period of time, usually between three and five years.

5. Initiating alternative strategies, and selecting specific strategies to achieve

Alternative strategies and special strategies set by management are to carry out various interesting activities that are liked by students, mosque-based education is not monotonous, but there must be interesting activities, such as activities outside the classroom. This is as stated by the chairman of the mosque prosperity board or knows as *DKM* of *al-Mukarromah* mosque with alternative strategy indicators, and choosing a specific strategy to be achieved in the formulation of the problem formulation of mosque-based education strategic management in developing children's personalities, the way is to adjust compulsory education with interspersed with interesting and extracurricular activities. liked by students, especially learning outing class.

Providing continuing education is also another special strategy implemented. Continuous education, meaning that education takes place continuously without stopping. Continuously, in the sense that learning is never finished, but continuously from a low level to a higher level, in accordance with the demands of change and development to acquire skills in life. Sustainable education is an effort to develop education, human resources (HR), and improve the standard of living of the community in accordance with the vision and mission of education that has been formulated.

Based on the explanation above, the researcher can conclude that alternative strategies and choosing specific strategies to

be achieved in the formulation of the problem formulation of mosque-based education strategic management in developing children's personality must be continuous and non-stop. Continuous in the sense that learning is never finished, but continuously from a low level to a higher level, in accordance with the demands of change and development to acquire skills in life.

CONCLUSION

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that the planning of strategic management of Al-Mukaromah mosque-based education uses several strategies to develop, prosper the mosque, namely by formulating starting with the development of the vision and mission, identify various opportunities and threats as well as strengths and weaknesses faced by the *al-Mukarromah* mosque, determine short-term, medium-term and long-term goals, and determine alternative strategies and specific strategies to achieve.

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